

TWINNING MATTERS..

When we connect, we create

WHAT?

A European Union programme that connects research teams across Europe. It helps universities and research centres grow stronger by teaming up with top scientific institutions.

WHY?

Boosting skills & research excellence

Building European partnership

Impact creation & sustainability

CHANGE

600 projects supported
3500+ researchers trained
38% higher proposal success rates
25 countries connected

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